

INDICATORS OF THE GLUTATHIONE SYSTEM IN THE ORAL FLUID OF CHILDREN WITH CHRONIC CATARRHAL GINGIVITIS AND UNDERLYING DIABETES MELLITUS**Kaskova L.***Poltava State Medical University,
Poltava, Ukraine***Honcharenko V.***Bukovinian State Medical University
Chernivtsi, Ukraine***Abstract**

The leading role in the development of periodontal diseases under the conditions of diabetes is played by the activation of peroxidation processes with the development of oxidative stress and the proper functioning of the antioxidant protection system, which regulates free radical processes in cells and tissues. The glutathione system, which includes glutathione itself and glutathione-dependent enzymes, binds free radicals, reduces peroxides, products of peroxidation of lipids, phospholipids of membranes, proteins, nucleic acids and removes them from the body in the form of non-toxic conjugates.

Therefore, the study of these indicators with the possibility of their regulation in the future is an important link in the prevention and treatment of dental diseases, including chronic catarrhal gingivitis.

A dental examination and laboratory study of the glutathione system of the oral fluid of 105 children aged 12 years of different observation groups will be carried out (children without background pathology with healthy periodontium (22 people - 1 group) and with chronic catarrhal gingivitis (18 people - 2 group), with the duration of the disease on diabetes under 5 years - 35 people (group 3), over 5 years - 30 people (group 4)). The following indicators were determined: the content of SH groups using Ellman reagent [I.F. Meshishen, N. Grigorieva, 2002]; glutathione -S - transferase activity by means of Habig W.H. method [1974]; glutathione reductase activity by means of Pinto R.E., Bartley V. method [1969]; glutathione peroxidase activity by means of Mogen V.M. method [1986]; glucose-6-phosphate dehydrogenase activity according to [Putilin F.E., Zoidze S.D., 1982], Hess, Scarnelli and Pierce.

The difference of all studied indicators in the children of the observation groups was revealed. Healthy children with intact periodontium had results that were significantly different from the other study groups. Thus, the G-SH index decreased depending on the state of the child's somatic health and the state of the periodontal tissues. In children with chronic catarrhal gingivitis on the background of diabetes mellitus, the indicators of glucose-6-phosphate dehydrogenase, glutathione peroxidase, glutathione reductase, glutathione transferase, reduced glutathione significantly worsened when the disease lasted more than 5 years compared to the indicators of other studied groups.

Keywords: children, chronic catarrhal gingivitis, diabetes mellitus, glutathione system, oral fluid.

Introduction. Many studies found the basic mechanisms and pathogenic significance of lipid peroxidation products in the pathogenesis of many diseases [1,3]. This also applies to dental pathology, especially with diseases of periodontal tissues, the condition of which worsens if children have an underlying pathology. Diabetes mellitus is currently quite common in children. Its severity and duration influence the manifestations of dental diseases [2]. The condition of periodontal tissues depends on local and general factors. A special place belongs to the functioning of the antioxidant defense system, which regulates free radical processes in cells and tissues and helps ensure free radical homeostasis in the body in general and in the oral cavity, in particular. The glutathione system, including glutathione itself and three enzymes (GP - glutathione peroxidase, GR - glutathione reductase, glutathione transferase), binds free radicals, reduces peroxides, lipid peroxidation products, membrane phospholipids, proteins, nucleic acids and removes them from the body in the form of non-toxic conjugates [4,5]. The sulfhydryl group (SH) is the main tool of glutathione in the implementation of antioxidant protection and detoxification effects [6]. Glucose-6-phosphate dehydrogenase (G-6 FDG) is a cytosolic enzyme involved in the process of

maintaining the level of reduced glutathione in the cell. GSH (GSH) - reduced glutathione is an intracellular antioxidant that inactivates free radicals [4].

Therefore, the study of these indicators with the possibility of their regulation in the future is an important link in the prevention and treatment of dental diseases, including chronic catarrhal gingivitis.

Objects and methods of the research. To achieve the purpose, dental and laboratory examination of 105 children at the age of 12 was carried out. The study involved 65 patients with diabetes mellitus undergoing inpatient treatment at the Pediatric Endocrinology Department of the Municipal Institution "Regional Pediatric Clinical Hospital" in Chernivtsi including those with the duration of the diseases up to 5 years - 35 individuals (group 3), longer than 5 years - 30 individuals (group 4). The groups of comparison involved the children without underlying pathology and healthy periodontium (22 individuals -1 group) and those with chronic catarrhal gingivitis (18 individuals - 2 group). Oral fluid for paraclinical study from children was collected in the morning after rinsing the oral cavity twice with purified water. The material was obtained by spitting without stimulation of salivation in a volume of 5-6ml. the material was transported and stored

at a temperature of -5°C . Before performing biochemical tests, the oral fluid was centrifuged for 15 minutes at a speed of 3000 rpm. The following indicators were determined:

- The content of SH groups using Ellman reagent [I.F. Meshishen, N. Grigorieva, 2002];
- Glutathione -S – transferase activity by means of Habig W.H. method [1974];
- glutathione reductase activity by means of Pinto R.E., Bartley V. method [1969]
- glutathione peroxidase activity by means of Mogen V.M. method [1986];
- Glucose-6-phosphate dehydrogenase activity according to [Putilin F.E., Zoidze S.D., 1982], Hess, Scarnelli and Pierce.

The material was statistically processed using Student's test. The results were considered reliable when $p < 0,05$.

Results and their discussion. We identified differences in all studied indicators in children of the observation groups. Healthy children with intact periodontium presented results that were significantly different from those of other study groups.

Thus, the G-SH indicator decreased depending on the state of the child's somatic health and the condition of the periodontal tissues. The lowest rate was found in children with chronic catarrhal gingivitis and diabetes

mellitus lasting more than 5 years. It was 2.18 times lower than in healthy children, 1.55 times lower than in somatically healthy children with chronic catarrhal gingivitis, 1.14 times lower than in children with chronic catarrhal gingivitis and diabetes mellitus lasting less than 5 years. In children with diabetes mellitus, the G-SH differed taking into account the duration of the underlying disease, but they were not significant, unlike the indicators of other study groups.

Similar situation was observed when studying enzymes (glutathione transferase (G-ST), glutathione peroxidase (GP), glutathione reductase (GR), which are directly involved in the processes of peroxidation, binding free radicals that produce a damaging effect on the tissues of the human body. In children, against the background diabetes mellitus indicators significantly worsen when the disease lasts more than 5 years in comparison with indicators in children of other study groups.

Glucose-6-phosphate dehydrogenase maintains the level of reduced glutathione, which is an intracellular antioxidant. Its decrease also contributes to a decrease in the level of reduced glutathione. Thus, a comparison of the indicators of children of groups 1 and 4 found a difference of 2.86 times, groups 2 and 4 - 1.66 times, groups 3 and 4 - 1.12 times.

Table

Indicators of the glutathione system in the oral fluid of children in observation groups ($M \pm m$)

Groups of children, number	Indicators of the glutathione system ($M \pm m$)				
	G-SH (kmol/mg of protein)	G-ST (nmol/min mg of protein)	GP (nmol/min mg of protein)	GR (nmol/min mg of protein)	G-6 FDG (nmol/min mg of protein)
1 group (n=22)	8,74±0,21	231,44±12,14	269,73±8,77	20,21±0,41	18,39±0,31
2 group (n=18)	6,2±0,09	161,37±4,85	396,15±5,70	13,62±0,19	10,68±0,16
p ¹	<0,05	<0,05	<0,05	<0,05	<0,05
3 group (n=35)	4,55±0,06	132,79±3,12	436,87±4,16	9,11±0,99	7,17±0,06
p ²	<0,05	<0,05	<0,05	<0,05	<0,05
p ³	<0,05	<0,05	<0,05	<0,05	<0,05
4 group (n=30)	4,01±0,11	116,69±2,49	459,28±3,44	8,04±0,08	6,43±0,06
p ⁴	<0,05	<0,05	<0,05	<0,05	<0,05
p ⁵	<0,05	<0,05	<0,05	<0,05	<0,05
p ⁶	>0,05	>0,05	>0,05	>0,05	>0,05

Notes:

- p1 – reliability of differences in indicators of children from 1 and 2 groups;
- p2 - reliability of differences in indicators of children from 1 и 3 groups;
- p3 - reliability of differences in indicators of children from 2 и 3 groups;
- p4 - reliability of differences in indicators of children from 1 и 4 groups;
- p5 - reliability of differences in indicators of children from 2 и 4 groups;
- p6 - reliability of differences in indicators of children from 3 и 4 groups.

Conclusions. The study of the glutathione system in the oral fluid of children demonstrated that healthy children with intact periodontium presented results that were significantly different from those of other study groups. In children with chronic catarrhal gingivitis against the background of diabetes mellitus, the indicators of glucose-6-phosphate dehydrogenase, glutathione peroxidase, glutathione reductase, glutathione transferase, and reduced glutathione significantly worsen when the disease lasts more than 5 years in

comparison with the indicators of children of other study groups.

Prospects of further studies. The results obtained require a more detailed study of the relationship between the processes of lipid peroxidation and the antioxidant protection of oral fluid in children with periodontal tissue diseases associated with diabetes mellitus. It will promote further development and creation of a

therapeutic complex aimed at regulating these processes, which will make it possible to reduce the incidence of periodontal tissue in this group of children.

References

1. Denysenko OI. Okysna modyfikatsiia bilkiv yak chynnyk patohenezu alerhodermatoziv. Ukrainnyi zhurnal dermatolohii, venerolohii, kosmetolohii. 2004;(1):23-6.
2. Markevych VE, Hlushchenko NV, Radchenko IP. Kliniko-epidemiolohichni osoblyvosti perebihu TsD 1-ho typu u ditei ta pidlitkiv. Visnyk Sumskoho derzhavnogo universytetu. 2011;(1):183-192.
3. Hnatiuk VV. Henderni ta vikovi osoblyvosti vilnoradykalnoho okysnennia ta antyoksydantnoho zakhystu pry desynkhronozii. Visnyk Vinnytskoho natsionalnoho medychnoho universytetu. 2014;(2):363-366.
4. Meshchyshen IF, Pishak VP, Hryhorieva NP. Hlutation: obmin i funktsii. Osnovy obminu rechovyn ta enerhii. Chernivtsi; 2005.s.123-130.
5. Babak O.Ia. Hlutation v normi ta pry patolohii: biolohichna rol i mozhlyvosti klinichnoho zastosuvannia. Zdorovia Ukrainy. 2015;(1):22-3.
6. Kozlov YuP. Perekysnoe okyslenye lypidov (POL) kak osnova svobodno-radykalnykh reaktsyi v kletkakh orhanyzma. Almanakh myrovoi nauky. 2016;(1):8-20.